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Intra-Sectoral Export Supply Capability Of Burundi

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The article investigated intra-sectoral export supply capability of Burundi. Using Balassa's revealed comparative advantage only two sectors namely, machinery/electrical and miscellaneous sectors showed some serious export supply capability. These sectors have 42 product codes and 34 products codes in which they have export supply capability respectively. Burundi has very limited comparative advantage. It is recommended that Burundi should put in place policies that attract foreign direct investment through transnational corporations that have the capability to transfer technology to Burundi that will enable it to produce efficiently. It is further recommended that Burundi should be exploring new natural endowments whose discovery can improve comparative advantage.

Keywords: Exports, International trade, comparative advantage, export capabilities.

INTRODUCTION

Generally, most of the studies are focused on comparative advantage of nations in terms of the products they produce and export. No efforts are made to investigate their export supply capabilities within sectors in a given country. The true picture of how the sectors are made and which sectors have great potential in a given country is never told. Most of the analyses are at product level not sectoral level as researchers devote their energy on identifying products without an identification of sectors to enable policy direction focused on sectors. This article investigates intra-sectoral export supply capabilities of Burundi.

COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE

There is no separate theory of comparative advantage for the sectors and individual products. The same theory is applicable in both contexts. This article therefore relies on the theory of comparative advantage to build its foundation for intra-sectoral export supply capabilities of Burundi. The theory of comparative advantage was developed by David Ricardo to advance his arguments against Corn Law. Corn Laws involved duties, subsidies and other hindrances put by the British Parliament in the 19th Century in order to prevent imports of grain while promoting the export of grain. David Ricardo was against the Corn Law and through his theory argued that specialization and trade without restrictions would lead to gains by all the trading parties involved and that real wages would increase in spite of the fact that parties being less efficient in production in absolute sense. A nation experiences an absolute advantage over another nation when it can produce a good by utilizing very little resources to produce it than the other nation would produce the same good. A nation experiences comparative advantage in producing a product when it is able to produce at least cost vis-à-vis other products (Case & Fair, 2002). In this case, it is not important to have an absolute advantage in order to benefit from international trade. What is most important is to have comparative advantage in a product over other products. According to Lee (1999), comparative advantage presents the same concerns as it does trade without restrictions (free trade). Trade without restrictions does not exert pressure on unemployment to increase or further does not depress wages. One of the ways available of increasing wages in a country is allowing workers in this country to face competition with workers of other nations via global trade. A nation can possess absolute advantage in producing a product without possession of comparative advantage. Comparative advantage influences the decision whether it is beneficial to produce a product and export it or not produce it and import it.

Comparative advantage is a phrase which is used to describe the ability of nations to export those products in which they are relatively endowed to produce compared to the rest of the world. If a nation is able to produce a product at a lower price than other nations, then in international trade, this nation should channel its resources to the production of such a product. By trading with other nations, it will be able to acquire other products at a minimum cost (opportunity cost) in return of its own product which it is able to produce efficiently (Serin & Civan, 2008).

The foundation of comparative advantage has now been established in terms of the products. It is no different than a nation will export output of the sectors that have comparative advantage and import goods that would have been produced in the sectors in which the country has no comparative advantage. By channeling resources to the sectors with comparative advantage, this will lead to efficient allocation of resources. If all the countries do like wise without any trade restriction the world welfare would increase. Governments can come up with policies that promote production in the identified sectors in which it has realistic export potential. These are the sectors which a country has capabilities to supply other nations which have comparative disadvantage in the product.

METHODOLOGY

In this article, the methodology used is Balassa (1965) index the revealed comparative advantage (RCA). According to Wu and Chen (2004) a higher RCA is evidence that a country possesses a greater revealed comparative advantage and competitive in the production of the product. Krugell and Matthee used Balassa (1965) method in comparing the strength of South African regions. Mzumara (2011) has used the technique to measure economic performance of Mozambique.

Balassa (1965) formula is as follows;

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{W,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{W,tot}} \right)$$

Where:

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports in the world.

An $RCA \geq 1$ demonstrates that a country has comparative advantage in the production of the same product. An $RCA < 1$ demonstrates that a country has no comparative advantage or lacks competitiveness in the production of the same product. According to Wu and Chen (2004) a higher RCA is evidence that a country possesses a greater revealed comparative advantage and competitive in the production of the product.

Export data used for Burundi and the world was obtained from International Trade Center on 6-digit level for 2008, 2009 and 2010. Data up to 2010 is available with the International Trade Centre.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Sectoral export supply capabilities results of Burundi are reported in table 1 below.

Table 1: Sectoral export supply capabilities of Burundi

Rank of the sector in export supply capabilities	Sector codes	Description of the sector	Number of product codes in which Burundi has export supply capabilities in each sector
1	84-85	Machinery/Electrical	42
2	90-97	Miscellaneous	34
3	06-15	Vegetable products	18
4	41-43	Raw hides, skins leather and furs	14

4	86-89	Transportation	14
5	28-38	Chemicals and allied industries	11
6	50-63	Textiles	9
6	72-83	Metals	9
7	16-24	Foodstuffs	8
7	44-49	Wood and wood products	8
8	25-27	Mineral products	6
9	68-71	Stone/glass	4
10	39-40	Plastics/Rubber	3
11	01-05	Animal and animal products	2
12	64-67	Footwear/Head gear	1

Source: From the results

In table1, column 1 shows the rank of each sector in terms of export supply capabilities. Column 2 represents sectoral codes. These are derived from the product codes as classified by the World Trade Organization and International Trade Centre. The first two digits of the product code represent the sector in which the product falls. Column 3 is the description in full of the relevant sector. Column 4 contains the number of product codes which have $RCA \geq 1$ in each sector. The higher the number of product codes the more capable is the sector in export supply. Machinery/Electrical sector is the most capable in export supply. It has 42 product codes in. It is followed by miscellaneous sector with 34 product codes. In third place are vegetable products with 18 product codes. In the fourth place are two sectors namely, raw hides, skins, leather and furs and transportation with 14 product codes each. The least capable export supply sector is foot wear/head gear. It has only 1 product code in it. It is followed by animal and animal products sector with only 2 product codes. In the third, least position is plastic/rubber with only 3 product codes. In terms of specialization according to the Theory of Comparative advantage is beneficial when a country channels its resources to the sector(s) in which it has comparative advantage in in the case of Burundi it will be sectors such as machinery/electrical. The products for such a sector are the ones that Burundi should be exporting. Then it needs to give up sectors such as foot wear/head gear in which it has very little comparative advantage and then just import the products in that sector. If all countries can adhere to such a pattern, the welfare of the world economy would improve significantly. Table 2 shows top 5-product codes in machinery/electrical in which Burundi has export supply capabilities.

Table 2: Top 5 product codes in which Burundi has export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	844851	Sinkers, needles etc for knitting, etc machines	11.87968	35.20896	41.67715	29.5886
2	845522	Cold metal rolling mills	27.6895	20.69533	23.67395	24.01959
3	845410	Converters used in metallurgy or metal foundries	59.66921	0	0	19.88974
4	845230	Sewing machine needles	14.97375	17.24658	16.24543	16.15525
5	847310	Parts and accessories of typewriters, word processors	44.91867	0	2.120854	15.67984

Source: From the results

In table 2, sinkers, needles etc for knitting, etc, machines product code has the highest export supply capabilities in machinery/electrical sector. It has an average RCA of 29.6. It is followed by cold metal rolling mills with an average index of 24.02. In the third place is converters used in metallurgy or metal foundries product code with an average index of 19.9. Sewing machine needles product code is in the fourth position with an average index of 16.2. In the fifth place are parts and accessories of typewriters, word processors product code with an average index of 15.7. This is the sector with largest number of product codes with export supply capabilities. It accounts for 42-product code. Table 3 shows top 5 product codes in miscellaneous sector with export supply capabilities.

Table 3: Top 5 product codes in miscellaneous sector with export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	911430	Clock or watch dials	3469.069	47551.611	4539.515	4253.398
2	900912	Electrostatic photocopiers, indirect process	0	10908.24	0	3636.081
3	900922	Contact type photocopying apparatus	77113.74	0	0	25704.58
4	911390	Watch straps etc parts, of leather/plastic	1248.398	1643.049	1781.598	1557.682
5	930119	Artillery weapons (eg guns, hotwizards and mortars) other than self propelled	2608.676	1185.878	833.3775	1542.644

Source: From the results.

In table 3, clock or watch dials product code has the highest average index in the miscellaneous sector. It has an average RCA of 4253.4. It is followed by electrostatic photocopiers, indirect process product code with an index of 3636.1. In the third place is contact type photocopying apparatus product code with an average index of 25704.6. In the fourth place is watch straps etc parts, of leather/plastic product code with an average index of 1557.7. The fifth place is artillery weapons product code with an average index of 1542.6. This sector has a total of 34 product codes with the export supply capabilities. Table 4 shows top 4 product codes in vegetable products sector with export supply capabilities.

Table 4: Top 4 product codes in vegetable products sector with export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	090111	Coffee, not roasted, not decaffeinated	277.5373	311.2705	492.8777	360.5618
2	090240	Tea, black (fermented or partly) in packages >3kg	255.7024	285.3957	369.4419	303.5133
3	090190	Coffee husks and skins	43.31698	138.3733	489.0154	223.5686
4	081090	Fruits, fresh	5.543962	304.8182	1.961493	104.1079

Source: From the results.

In table 4, coffee, not roasted, not decaffeinated product code has the highest export capability in the vegetable products sector. It has an average index of 360.6. It is followed by tea black (fermented or partly) in packages >3kg product code. It has the average index of 303.5. In the third place is coffee husks and skins product code with an average index 223.6. In the fourth place is a fruit, fresh product code with an average index of 104.1. The sector has

a total of 18 product codes with export supply capabilities. Table 5 shows top 3-product code in raw hides, skins, leather and furs sector with export supply capabilities.

Table 5: Top 3 product codes in raw hides, skins, leather and furs sector with export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	410320	Reptiles skins, raw	27394.78	88979.11	0	38791.29
2	410120	Whole bovine (including buffalo/equine hides and skins)	210.9655	80.61768	113.364	134.9824
3	410691	Tanned/crust hides and skins without wool/hair on in the wet state	143.4118	433.1246	0	2.041898

In table 5, reptiles' skins, raw product code has the highest export supply capability in raw hides, skins, leather and furs sector. It has an average index of 38791.3. It is followed by whole bovine (including buffalo/equine hides and skins) product code with an index of 135. In the third place is Tanned/crust hides and skins without wool/hair on in the wet state with an index of 2. In total, there are 14 product codes in this sector with export supply capabilities the same number of codes with transportation sector. Table 6 shows top 3 product codes in transportation sector with export supply capabilities.

Table 6: Top 3 product codes in transportation sector with export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	880400	Parachutes, parts and accessories thereof	186.6715	101.5376	207.1309	195.1133
2	880220	Fixed wing aircraft, unladen weight <2000kg	20.09861	49.65967	49.87944	39.87924
3	870422	Diesel powered trucks weighing 5-20 tones	1.516987	39.39976	0.932419	13.94972

Source: From the results

In table 6, parachutes, parts and accessories thereof product code has the highest export supply capability in the transportation sector. It has the index of 195.1. It is followed by fixed wing aircraft, unladen weight <2000kg product code with an index of 39.9. In the third place is diesel powered trucks weighing 5-20 tones with an index of 13.9. Transportation sector has total of 14 product codes with export supply capabilities like raw, hides, skins leather and furs sector. Table 7 shows top 3 product code in chemicals and allied industries sector with export supply capability.

Table 7: Top 3 product code in chemicals and allied industries sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	340111	Soaps, for toilet use, solid	40.78897	54.96759	59.53096	51.76251
2	290410	Sulphunoted hydrocarbons, salts and ethylesters	0	0	14.46786	4.82262
3	340219	Organic surface-active agents	6.420139	2.692673	1.553903	3.555572

Source: From the results.

In table 7, soaps, for toilet use, solid product code has the highest export supply capability in the chemicals and allied industries sector. It has an average index of 51.8. It is followed by sulphunoted hydrocarbons, salts and ethylesters product code with an average index of 4.8. In the third place is organic surface-active agent's product code with an index of 3.6. In total, there are 11 product codes with export supply capability in the chemicals and allied industries. Table 8 shows top 3 product codes in the textiles sector with export supply capability.

Table 8: Top 3 product codes in textiles sector with export supply capability.

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	520291	Garneted stock of cotton	0	3848.992	0	1282.997
2	520300	Cotton carded or combed	440.216	356.3668	657.2575	484.6134
3	620329	Men's, boys' ensembles, of material not knit	0	0	68.17933	22.72644

Source: From the results

In Table 8, garneted stock of cotton product code has the highest export supply capability in the textiles sector. It has an average index of 1283. It is followed by cotton carded or combed product code with an average index of 484.6. In the third place is men's, boys' ensembles, of material not knit product code with an average index of 22.7. In total, the sector has 9 product codes with export supply capability being at par with metals sector. Table 9 shows top 3 product codes in metals sector with export supply capability.

Table 9: Top 3 product codes in metals sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	811213	Beryllium waste and scrap	0	0	635.6153	211.8718
2	800400	Tin plates, sheets and strips, thickness >0.2mm	240.7354	0	0	80.24515
3	720429	Waste or scrap, of alloy steel, other than stainless	46.3205	77.05302	74.72142	66.03165

Source: From the results.

In Table 9, beryllium waste and scrap product code has the highest export supply capability in the metals sector. It has an index of 211.9. It is followed by tin plates, sheets and strips, thickness >0.2mm product code with an average index of 80.2. In the third place is waste or scrap, of alloy steel, other than stainless product code has an average index of 66. There are total of 9 product codes in this sector. That gives it at par with textiles sector. Table 10 shows top 3 product codes in foodstuffs sector with export supply capability.

Table 10: Top 3 product codes in the foodstuffs sector with export supply capabilities

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	220300	Beer made from malt	15.62858	15.10168	20.46355	17.0646
2	220600	Fermented beverages (eg cider, perry, mead, etc)	29.17938	0.10828	0	9.762553
3	240220	Cigarettes containing tobacco	9.455662	8.860909	9.936203	9.417592

Source: From the results

In Table 10, beer made from malt product code has the highest export supply capability in the foodstuffs sector. It has an average index of 17. It is followed by fermented beverages (eg cider, perry, mead, etc) product code with an average index of 9.8. In the third place is cigarettes containing tobacco product code with an index of 9.4. In all, the sector has 8 product codes with export supply capability. The same product code number is shared with wood and wood products sector. Table 11 shows top 3 product codes in the wood and wood product sector with export supply capability.

Table 11: Top 3 product codes in wood and wood products sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	481390	Paper, cigarette except in rolls <5cm wide	17.74931	35.44615	89.07971	47.42506
2	481850	Clothing and accessories of paper	73.79826	23.30513	30.2537	42.45236
3	481500	Floor coverings on a base paper	122.6192	0	0	40.87306

Source: From the results.

In Table 11, paper, cigarette except in rolls <5cm wide product code has the highest export supply capability. It has an average index of 47.4. It is followed by clothing and accessories of paper product code with an index average of 42.45236. In the third place are floor coverings on a base paper product code with an index average of 40.9. The entire sector has 8 product codes in which it has export supply capability. It is par with foodstuffs sector in terms of number of product code. Table 12 shows top 3 product codes in mineral products sector with export supply capability.

Table 12: Top 3 product codes in mineral products sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	261790	Ores and concentrates	476.8861	293.0178	122.3671	297.4237
2	261590	Niobium, tantalum and vanadium ores and concentrates	803.8285	0	0	267.9428
3	260900	Tin ores and concentrates	66.05901	65.99469	91.80512	74.61961

Source: From the results

In Table 12, ores and concentrates product code has the highest export supply capability in the mineral sector with an average index of 297.4. It is followed by niobium, tantalum and vanadium ores and concentrates with an average index of 267.9. In the third place is tin ores and concentrates with an average index of 74.6. In all mineral products sector has only 6 product codes with export supply capabilities. Table 13 shows top 3 product codes in stone/glass sector with export supply capability.

Table 13: Top 3 product codes in stone/glass sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	710811	Gold powder non-monetary	0	1841.686	45.80607	629.164
2	710812	Gold in unwrought forms non-monetary	93.92856	33.05616	17.35515	48.11329
3	701090	Glass containers for packing or conveyance goods	4.3055551	0.212345	0.561158	1.693018

Source: From the results

In Table 13, gold powder non-monetary product code has the highest export supply capability in the stone/glass sector with an average index of 629.2. It is followed by gold in unwrought forms non-monetary product code with an average index of 48.1. Glass containers for packing or conveyance goods product code comes in the third place with an average index of 1.7. There are only 4 product codes with export supply capability in this sector. Table 14 shows all product codes in plastics/rubber sector with export supply capability.

Table 14: All product codes in plastics/rubber sector with supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	401220	Pneumatic tyres used	0	47.25967	0	15.75322
2	391890	Floor/wall/ceiling cover, roll/tile not vinyl chloride	0	16.59827	1.022562	5.87361
3	392310	Boxes, cases, crates etc of plastic	6.420139	2.692673	1.553903	3.555572

Source: From the results.

In Table 14, pneumatic tyres used product code has the highest export supply capability in the plastic/rubber sector with an average index of 15.8. In the second place is floor/wall/ceiling cover, roll/tile not vinyl chloride product code with an average index of 5.9. Boxes, cases crates etc of plastic code with an average index of 3.6 is in the third place. There are only 3 product codes in the plastic/rubber sector with export supply capability. Table 15 shows all product codes in animal and 1

Table 15: All product codes in plastic/rubber sector with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	030110	Ornamental fish, live	69.26128	74.65214	65.39674	69.77005
2	030191	Trout, live	0	4.315824	0	1.438608

Source: From the results.

Ornamental fish, live product code in table 15 has the highest export supply capability in the plastic/rubber sector with an average index of 69.8. Trout, live product code is in second position with an average index of 1.4. There are only two product codes in the plastic/rubber sector with export supply capability. Table 16 shows the only product code in foot wear/head gear with export supply capability.

Table 16: The only product code in foot wear/head gear with export supply capability

Rank	Product code	Product description	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	2010 RCA	Average RCA
1	640110	Water proof foot wear (wellington etc) metal toe cap	0	0	30.6621	10.2207

Source: From the results

Waterproof footwear (wellington etc) metal toe cap product code is the only one with export supply capability in the foot wear/head gear with an index of 10.2.

Generally, Burundi is constrained by limited number of product codes in which it has export supply capability. As a result, sector export supply capability is very weak as few product codes fall in them. It is very difficult to come up with sectoral policies when there are no enough products in each sector. Except machinery/electrical and miscellaneous sectors, the rest of other sectors have very fewer products in them. There is very limited scope of comparative advantage in Burundi's foreign sector.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Burundi possesses very weak intra-sectoral export supply capability. The only sectors that demonstrate significant export capability are machinery/electrical and miscellaneous sectors. There are fewer products with export supply capability. With very few sectors with export supply capability, Burundi benefits from international trade may be limited. It is recommended that Burundi should improve in efficiency in its production. One of the ways this can be achieved is through attracting foreign direct investment (FDI). Investment by transnational corporation in Burundi can bring technology that can improve its efficiency in production. It is also recommended that Burundi should continue exploring for new natural endowments whose discovery can lead to some comparative advantage.

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